

Extraction of Chromium(VI) from Mineral Acid Solutions

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The extraction of Chromium(VI) into trilauryl amine (TLA) in chloroform, from aqueous perchloric, hydrochloric, sulfuric and nitric acids has been studied. The extraction from aqueous perchloric acid is negligible. The extractions from hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions are quantitative and partial from aqueous nitric acid solutions. The species extracted from hydrochloric and sulfuric acid media are identified.

SEVERAL workers^{1,2} have studied the extraction of Chromium(VI) by tributylphosphate, tertiaryamines and related systems from various acid solutions. The solvent extraction behaviour of Chromium(VI) from orthophosphoric acid solutions using TLA as extractant was earlier reported by us³ and the extracted species was identified as $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$.

Deptula^{4,5} reported that, in the extraction of chromium(VI) from hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions into tertiary amine, tri-n-octyl amine, the extracted species are CrO_3Cl^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ respectively.

The present communication describes our studies with radiotracers, on the extraction of chromium(VI) into TLA from dilute hydrochloric, sulfuric, nitric and perchloric acid solutions.

Experimental

Materials : Chromic acid (E. Merck) was used for preparing chromium(VI) stock solutions.

Trilaurylamine supplied as a gift by M/s. General Mills, Kankakee, Illinois was used without any further purification. All other chemicals were of analytical grade or samples purified according to the standard methods.

Chromium-51 in the form of sodium chromate in isotonic saline solution (15 mCi/mg sp. activity), chlorine-36 as hydrochloric acid solution (5-25 mCi/g sp. activity) and sulfur-35 as sulfuric acid in dilute hydrochloric acid solution (carrier free) were obtained from Isotope Division, BARC, Bombay.

Equipment : A single channel analyser SC 600 (Electronics Corporation of India Ltd.) coupled with 3" well type scintillation detector (Nuclear Chicago) was used for γ -activity measurements. Liquid β -activities were measured using a scintillation counting assembly with a mixture of 10% naphthalene, 0.03% POPOP (1,4 bis-2,5 phenyloxazolyl benzene), 2% TOPO and 0.7% PPO (2,5 phenyl oxazole) in dioxan as liquid scintillator solution.

Absorption spectra were taken on a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer.

Distribution coefficient (k_d) measurements : Measurements of k_d were made according to the procedure described earlier³.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of chromium(VI) as a function of acidity : There was no change in k_d upto 1.0M acid beyond which a gradual fall was observed in the case of hydrochloric as well as sulfuric acid solutions. This fall may be due to the reduction of chromium(VI) to Chromium(III) as indicated by the characteristic green coloration in the aqueous phase. The extractions are quantitative upto 1.0M hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions. On the other hand the extraction was partial from nitric acid solutions with a gradual fall in k_d with the variation of acidity even below 1.0M. In contrast extraction from perchloric acid solutions was negligible, the extraction not exceeding 5% upto 1.0M perchloric acid.

Composition of the extracted species : In order to determine the composition of the extracted species the extraction isotherm⁶ method and the distribution coefficient method⁷ were employed. A plot of $[\text{Cr}_{org}]$ vs $[\text{Cr}_{aq}]$ gave an extraction isotherm (Fig. 1) which rises steeply to a maximum value and remains practically constant thereafter. The ratio of concentrations of TLA to the maximum concentration of chromium(VI) extracted corresponds to a value of unity $[(\text{TLA})/(\text{Cr})=1]$ in hydrochloric and sulfuric acid systems. In the distribution studies (Fig. 2) from hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions straight lines with slopes 1.02 and 2.07 respectively are obtained. These results indicate the presence of chromium(VI) and TLA in 1 : 1 ratio in the species extracted from hydrochloric acid while it is present in 1 : 2 ratio in the species extracted from sulfuric acid media.

Fig. 1. Extraction Isotherm with 0.025 M TLA.

Fig. 2. Distribution of Chromium (VI) as a function of TLA concentration.

Extractions were carried out varying the concentrations of chromium(VI) from constant hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions containing respective ^{36}Cl and ^{35}S tracers with 0.025 M TLA preequilibrated with 0.1 N respective acids. Fig. 3 shows the distribution of acid in the organic phase as a function of chromium(VI) in the aqueous phase. It is seen that the distribution of chloride in the organic phase with the variation of Chromium(VI) in the aqueous phase decreased

upto a certain value and remained constant thereafter. The chloride concentration corresponding to this constant value is less than the chromium (VI) concentration in the organic phase. This clearly shows that the extracted chromium (VI) is present as a mixture of species containing predominantly CrO_3Cl^- (Table 1). Distribution studies from sulfuric acid solutions using ^{35}S as radiotracer (Fig. 3) indicate that the distribution of sulfate in the organic phase decreased as the chromium(VI) concentration is increased and finally as the chromium(VI) concentration becomes equal or greater than the amine concentration, the sulfate concentration approaches zero indicating that no sulfate is retained in the organic phase (Table 2).

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF ORGANIC PHASE UNDER SATURATION CONDITION WITH CHROMIUM (VI).

TLA=0.025 M			HCl=0.10 M		
Initial Cr Conc. Aq. phase	Conc. of Org. phase (M)		Molar ratio		
M	Cr	Cl ⁻	Cr	TLA	Cl ⁻
0.030	0.025	0.0195	1	1	0.78
0.030	0.025	0.0192	1	1	0.77
0.035	0.025	0.0181	1	1	0.72
0.040	0.025	0.0180	1	1	0.72
0.050	0.025	0.0180	1	1	0.72

TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF THE ORGANIC PHASE UNDER SATURATION CONDITION WITH CHROMIUM (VI).

TLA=0.025 M			$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.05 M$		
Initial Conc. Aq. phase (M)	Conc. of Org. phase (M)		Molar ratio		
	Cr	SO_4^{2-}	Cr	TLA	SO_4^{2-}
0.025	0.0246	0.0019	1	1	0.06
0.030	0.0250	0.0009	1	1	0.035
0.035	0.0250	0.00085	1	1	0.035
0.040	0.0250	0.00285	1	1	0.035
0.050	0.0250	0.00085	1	1	0.035

Absorption spectra : The above findings are further confirmed by measurement of absorption spectra of chromium(VI) in the organic phase. The individual chromium(VI) compounds can be identified on the basis of their differences in the absorption in the ultraviolet region^{1,8,9,10}. The characteristic absorption maxima for CrO_3Cl^- are at 230 nm, 288 nm and 355 nm and those for $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ are at 280 and 355 nm. The absorption spectra of chromium(VI) in the organic phase obtained by extraction at various aqueous acid concentrations, keeping the aqueous chromium(VI) concentration constant was found to exhibit absorption maxima at 285 nm and 355 nm (Fig. 4) in hydrochloric and sulfuric acid systems. As the spectra were taken with chloroform as solvent for which the cut off point in the UV region is at 245 nm the absorption maximum at 230 nm for the species CrO_3Cl^- could not be identified. Hence a comparison of the ratio of the molar extinctions at 285 nm and 355 nm as a function of acid

Fig. 3. Distribution of Chloride and Sulfate as a function of Chromium (VI) concentration with 0.025 M TLA.

In aqueous systems Chromium(VI) exhibits various equilibria^{1,8,9,11}.

Under our experimental conditions the predominant species appear to be CrO_3Cl^- , HCr_2O_7^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$. The data show a mixture of species predominantly CrO_3Cl^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and/or HCr_2O_7^- is extracted from hydrochloric acid media confirming the mechanism suggested by Deptula⁴. The extracted species from sulfuric acid solutions is exclusively $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ extracted as $(\text{R}_3\text{NH}^+)_2 \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$.

molarity is taken as the criterion for identifying the species. These ratios varied with the change in the concentration of the aqueous hydrochloric acid, indicating the presence of a mixture of species. On the other hand the ratio was constant confirming the presence of a single species in sulfuric acid solutions (ratio is ~2) corresponding to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$.

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Fig. 4. Absorption Spectra of Chromium (VI) in organic phases (0.025 M TLA) obtained by extraction from various aqueous acid concentrations using 0.020 M aqueous Chromium (VI) concentration.

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